

Employees' Satisfaction and Firms' Performance: Evidence from Small and Medium Enterprises in Burundi

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Abstract

The study's objective is to assess the impact of employees' satisfaction on firms' performance in Burundi with a focus on the Agro-food SMEs. The study sampled 369 respondents for its data and used SPSS ordinary least square method to analyze its data. In conclusion, the study found a positive and statistically significant impact of employees' satisfaction on firms' performance and the satisfaction of employees stems from their level of education and number of years in employment. However, employers should prioritize the plights of their employees to ensure higher productivity. Perhaps, employees play crucial role in the success of every organization.

Keywords: *Employees' satisfaction; Firms' performance; Burundi; Small and Medium enterprises*

1. Introduction

The important characteristics of an organization have lately been overlooked thus employees' attitude towards work thus motivation for job satisfaction through loyalty and commitment (Boudreau et al., 2003; 2004). Many organizations are now focused on the "operation-centric approach" which eliminates the prioritization of human resources. As the world economy has emerged into a single market through globalization, organizations are looking for competitive means to sustain their operations due to the consequences of globalization, such as increase in competitive markets and the dynamism of market volatility. Nonetheless, prior studies have centered on the priority of increasing operational efficiency and service quality through optimizing, designing and delivering systems for service delivery (Hill, 2007; Saccania et al., 2007; Frie et al., 1999).

Employees are insiders of organizations and their dealings are observed directly to the effect of changes or variations in policies, products and services that ensued in the organization. However, their involvement in product development stages and promotion of new products or services boosts their morale and affirms their belongingness to the organization to have sense of accomplishment. Theoretically, it is not clear as to how changes in the satisfaction of employees will significantly affect the performance of firms in the future. Moreover, if a firm diverts its resources into increasing the pay or salary of its employees to satisfy them at the disadvantage of its shareholders, then it is expected the increase in the employees' satisfaction as in the pay rise will negatively affect the performance of the firms in the future. This assumption is supported by the studies from Abowd (1989) and Gorton and Schmid (2004) as they inferred that an increase in pay or salaries of employees would literally reduce the market value of the firm and the greater a firm involves its employees in their operations of the firm will affect the valuation and profitability in the long run. Contrary, scores of literature are on divergent views; McGregor (1960) suggested that highly motivated employees induce efficiency and effectiveness in the workplace to translate into higher productivity and profitability. Basically, it helps in achieving the objectives and goals of the firm. To buttress this view, the efficiency wage theory posits that no satisfied employee will seek his/her dismissal due to the level of satisfaction been given by the firm. Hence, highly satisfied employees produce higher results and work tirelessly to achieve set objectives and targets assigned to them (Akerlof & Yellen, 1986; Akerlof, 1982).

Eventually, the above views from these prolific researchers have posited this study in order to test the hypothesis that employees' satisfaction significantly influences the performance of firms. Many studies focused on the service industries to unravel the impact of employees' satisfaction on customer services (Chase, 1981;

Heskett et al., 1994; Oliva & Sterman, 2001). In lieu of this, the scope of this study will be focused on the Agro-food Small and Medium Enterprises in Burundi, Bujumbura, to be precise.

The content of the study is as follows: section 1 introduces the study and reviews of some literature, section 2 presents the research data and methodology, section 3 consists of the findings discussion and conclusion, section for highlights on the limitation of the study and future direction.

1.1 Employees satisfaction and Firms' performance

Empirically, enormous studies have investigated the nexus between employees' satisfaction and firms' performance. Seemingly, the question that crops up when these investigations are undertaken is "do changes in employee satisfaction significantly influence the performance of firms?" Perhaps, it is an advantage for firms with higher regard in information asymmetries and highly considers human capital development to have positive and stronger effect on their performance. The likes of Faleye and Trahan (2006), Edmans (2011) and Filbeck and Preece (2003) shared the same opinion that employees' satisfaction highly and significantly influences the performance of firms. Consequentially, firm that prioritizes the welfare of its employees potentially enjoys higher productivity. In the long run, satisfied employees through motivations outperform to help increase the size of their firms and also promote value creation by ensuring customers are inculcated into their business operation to ensure sustainability and profitability.

In furtherance, a critical look into organizational behavior and its relationship with effectiveness of organizations resulted that the attitudes of employees are crucial to the survival and effectiveness of an organization; this usually affects the profitability and productivity of organizations (Meyer et al., 2004; Vroom, 1964; Schwab & Cummings, 1970; Becker et al., 1996). Their studies they share the view that satisfied employees through loyalty and commitment serve customers in efficient and effective manner (Loveman, 1998; Silvestro & Cross, 2000; Yoon & Suh, 2003).

Arguably, scores of studies have presented different views as these school of thought posit that employees' satisfaction has less impact on firms' performance (Mathieu & Zajac, 1990), even though some studies have concluded that there is a correlation between employee satisfaction with sabotage, turnover, lateness, absenteeism and drug use (Fisher & Locke, 1992) and the relationship between employee satisfaction and firms' performance in terms of research is sparse (Nagar & Rajan, 2005; Heim & Singa, 2001; Balasubramanian et al., 2003) affirmed. Roth and Jackson III (1995) postulated that employees have in-depth information and knowledge about the products and services of a firm hence they have the upper hand in determining the quality of services and also have the capacity to influence the performance of the market. In spite of this, quality of service provided will drastically reduce if firms become "leaner and efficient" through factor productivity.

In a review of the above literature, the study is of the view that employees' satisfaction could significantly affect the performance of firms by considering certain characteristics of the employees. Moreover, it assumed that small firms experience constraints by resources of the organization perhaps they highly rely on their employees' satisfaction individually to provide quality goods and services (McCartan-Quinn & Carson, 2003; Haugh & Mckee, 2004; Coviello et al., 2006) hence the development of the hypotheses below:

H1: Employees' satisfaction positively and significantly impact firms' performance

H2: The age of employees significantly impact firms' performance.

H3: The gender of employees significantly impact firms' performance.

H4: The years of employment of employees positively and significantly impact firms' performance.

H5: The level of education of employees positively and significantly impact firms' performance.

2. Research Methodology

2.1 Sample and data collection

The study in its previous survey to strongly affirm that the questionnaires are suitable conducted a pilot study with 60 respondents. The results confirmed that the questionnaire was suitable for the study. The pilot study was conducted due to the limitations that may arise such as time constraints and educational factors, as in clarity of the questionnaire. The survey was conducted in Bujumbura, the capital of Burundi. As the scope of the study was centered on agro-food SMEs, the respondents were employees of such enterprises. The study used a convenient random sampling technique to collect its data. However, the sample was 369 that represented the population of employees in the agro-food SMEs in the country. The descriptive statistics of the respondents can be found in the table below;

Table 1 Descriptive statistics of demographics

Demographics	Number of respondents	Percentage
Gender		
Male	196	53.1%
Female	173	46.9%
Total	396	100%
Age		
16 years to 25 years	107	29.0%
26 years to 35 years	90	24.4%
36 years to 45 years	153	41.5%
Above 45 years	19	5.1%
	369	100%
Number of years as an employee		
1 year to 5 years	98	26.6%
6 years to 10 years	253	68.6%
Above 10 years	18	4.8%
	369	100%
Level of Education		
Junior High Education	120	32.5%
Senior High Education	196	53.1%
Bachelor	50	13.6%
Masters	3	0.8%
	369	100%

2.2 Variable measurements and model specification

In order to examine the constructs thus the variables, the study considered a 7 point Likert scale for the questions due to its statistical reliability. The range of the Likert scale was used to measure the items thus employees' satisfaction and firms' performance; the scale for employees' performance ranged from 1- totally disagree to 7 – totally agree and the scale for firms' performance ranged from 1 – much lower to 7 – much higher.

The study used an econometric model, thus ordinary least square to analysis its data. The model for the study can be written as

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_k X_k + \varepsilon$$

In the above equation, Y represents the dependent variable (Firms performance), β_0 represents regression coefficient of the intercept/constant, $\beta_1 X_1$ refers to the regressors or predictors and the slope coefficients or independent variables, $\beta_k X_k$ represents the control variables (demographics: age, years of employment, gender and level of education) and ε represents the stochastic error term or disturbance that cannot be estimated for by the independent variables.

2.3 Construct validity and reliability

According to Nunnally (1978), the rule of thumb of Cronbach Alpha (CA) posits that the coefficient value of CA should be higher than 0.70. However, there are four main standards for checking the validity of constructs thus Cronbach Alpha (Hinton et al., 2004). The first standard posits that when the coefficient value of Cronbach Alpha is with 0.70 and 0.90, it is termed as high reliability. The second standard posits that when the coefficient value falls within 0.50 and 0.70, it is termed as moderate reliability. The third standard posits that when the coefficient value falls below 0.50 then it is termed as weak reliability. The study's constructs had Cronbach Alpha coefficients had the highest of 0.869 and lowest of 0.667 which passed the average value of 0.50. Therefore, the study can confidently confirm that its constructs are reliable for its analysis. Moreover, it can be found from table 2 that the composite reliability (CR) test for the construct was significant. Thus the constructs had a coefficient value of 0.920 and 0.795, respectively, which surpassed the standard or rule of thumb value of 0.70 (Gefen et al., 2000). In addition, the AVE for the construct had significant values as the lowest value was 0.565 and the highest was 0.741. According to Bagozzi & Yi (1988) the AVE statistical coefficient value should above 0.50 to be considered significant. The validity and reliability test for the study have all been considered significant therefore it paves the way for further analysis.

In order to ascertain the discriminant validity coefficients or in other words correlation coefficients the study's dependent and independent variables, two approaches were considered in that order. The approaches were used to ensure that the indicators of cross-loadings were greater than the opposing constructs and also each construct AVE was square root (Fornell & Larcker, 1981; Hair et al., 2012). In brief, the study confirms that the methods or approaches used provided satisfactory validity or results (See Table 3).

Table 2 Construct validity and reliability

		Loadings	CA	CR	AVE
Employees Satisfaction					
ES1	I am satisfied with the salary of this company.	0.869	0.884	0.920	0.741
ES2	I am satisfied with the promotion opportunity of this company.	0.839			
ES3	I am satisfied with the relationship of my fellow workers of this company.	0.875			
ES4	I am satisfied with the supervision of my supervisor of this company.	0.861			
Firms' Performance					
FP1	Return on assets	0.781	0.614	0.795	0.565
FP2	Return on sales	0.667			
FP3	Return on investment	0.800			

Table 3 Discriminant validity coefficients

	ES	FP	EDUCATION	GENDER	AGE	YEARSOFEMP
ES	0.861*					
FP	0.803	0.752*				
EDUCATION	0.644	0.734	0.861*			
GENDER	0.556	0.675	0.733	0.810*		
AGE	-0.138	-0.126	-0.124	-0.07	1	
YEARSOFEMP	0.603	0.543	0.439	0.613	0.159	0.757*

Note: ES refers to employees' satisfaction, FP refers to firms' performance; EDUCATION refers to the level of education, YEARSOFEMP refers to years of employment.

3. Findings discussion and conclusion

From table 4 the analysis of the study's data can be found. The study focused on the Agro-food SMEs due to the fewer literature in that sector. Previous studies have found a positive relationship between employee satisfaction and firms' performance; this motivated the study to probe further to ascertain whether that relationship exists in the agro-food sector of Burundi. Hence, the study sampled 369 respondents for its data. However, the data was analyzed by using econometric model thus ordinary least square method and the results can be found in table 4. The hypotheses of the study were five. Hypothesis 1 stated that employee satisfaction positively and significantly impact firms' performance and the results confirm that there is a positive and statistically impact of employees' satisfaction on firms' performance with unstandardized coefficient of 0.532 and standardized coefficient of 0.493 at 1% significant level. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted that there is positive and significant impact on employees' satisfaction on firms' performance. To account for the control variables as were hypothesized; hypothesis 2 posits that age of employees has significant impact on firms' performance. From the table, it can be reported that the age of employees has an insignificant impact on firms' performance as well as the gender of employees. Hence hypotheses two and three are rejected. However, the years that employees have been in employment and their level of education have positive and statistically significant impact on firms' performance. In this regard, hypotheses 4 and 5 have been accepted. In other words, the higher the number of years that an employee spends in the firm, the higher the satisfaction of the employee and contribute positively to firms' performance as well as the higher the level of education of an employee, the higher the satisfaction of the employee in the firm which positively impact firm's performance.

On this premise, the study would like to affirm the assertion that happy employees grow successful organizations. For a business to flourish and prosper, then it needs to cater to its employees to ensure higher productivity, which in the long run will translate into profitability and sustainability. Employees' satisfaction should be prioritized by every organization that seems to grow in order to achieve its goals and vision.

Table 4 Regression analysis with Ordinary least square

Firms' Performance	Unstandardized coefficient	standardized coefficient	t-statistics	p-value
employee satisfaction	0.532	0.493	7.441**	0.000
Age	-0.083	0.074	-1.000	0.319
Gender	-0.151	-0.070	-1.079	0.282
Years of employment	0.261	0.324	4.595**	0.000
level of education	0.432	0.432	6.237**	0.000
constant	2.188		5.811**	0.000
Model fitness				
R	0.710			
R2	0.504			
Adjusted R2	0.49			
F-statistics	37.073**			

Note: ** indicates 1% significance level

4. Limitation and future direction

The study focused on Burundi and centered in one city thus Bujumbura. However, it only focused on the agro-food SMEs and no mediating or moderating effects were inculcated into the study. Therefore, this creates a

limitation to study perhaps future studies can focus on involving variables that could affect the relationship between employees' satisfaction and firms' performance as mediators or moderators. Most importantly, employers should endeavor to prioritize the plights of their employees to ensure high productivity at work for a positive work environment.

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